

LETTING STUDENTS MAKE MISTAKES LEADS TO SUCCESS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: It might be difficult to teach children a new language, but it gets considerably more difficult when teachers try to totally avoid making mistakes. A tight and controlled learning environment is frequently brought about by the fear of making mistakes, which can impede students' development and constrict their creativity. On the other hand, allowing students to make mistakes is a good strategy to encourage self-correction, critical thinking, and language confidence. Without some degree of trial and error, pupils may find it difficult to learn English because it is a complex language with many rules and exceptions. Teachers can assist students in overcoming their concerns and improving their language abilities by creating a safe, encouraging environment where it is acceptable to make mistakes. In this article, we will discuss the advantages of allowing students to make mistakes when teaching English and offer useful tactics that teachers can employ to motivate students to take calculated chances and learn from their failures. We will also go over the value of giving students constructive criticism and encouragement as well as how teachers can strike the perfect balance between correcting errors and letting students learn from them.

Keywords: overcorrection, knowledge gap, metacognition, error-filled speech, self-correct, phonemic chart, direct adjustments, perplexing, linguistic input, graphically display

РАЗРЕШЕНИЕ УЧАЩИМСЯ СОВЕРШАТЬ ОШИБКИ ПРИВОДИТ К УСПЕХУ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация: Возможно, трудно обучать детей новому языку, но это становится значительно сложнее, когда учителя пытаются полностью избежать ошибок. Жесткая и контролируемая среда обучения часто возникает из-за страха совершить ошибки, которые могут препятствовать развитию учащихся и ограничивать их творческие способности. С другой стороны, позволять учащимся совершать ошибки - хорошая стратегия поощрения самокоррекции, критического мышления и уверенности в языке. Без определенной степени проб и ошибок учащимся может быть трудно изучать английский язык, потому что это сложный язык со множеством правил и исключений. Учителя могут помочь учащимся преодолеть свои проблемы и улучшить свои языковые способности, создав безопасную, поощряющую среду, в которой допустимо совершать ошибки. В этой статье мы обсудим преимущества предоставления учащимся возможности совершать ошибки при преподавании английского языка и предложим полезные тактики, которые учителя могут использовать, чтобы мотивировать учащихся использовать просчитанные шансы и извлекать уроки из своих неудач. Мы также обсудим ценность конструктивной критики и поощрения учащихся, а также то, как учителя могут найти идеальный баланс между исправлением ошибок и предоставлением учащимся возможности учиться на них.

Ключевые слова: коррекция ошибок, пробел в знаниях, метапознание, речь с ошибками, самокоррекция, фонематическая таблица, прямые корректировки, недоумение, лингвистический ввод, графическое отображение

INTRODUCTION

The knowledge, abilities, and character development of individuals are significantly influenced by their education. There has always been limited opportunity for error in the classroom since it emphasizes the quest of excellence. Recent instructional strategies, however, acknowledge the importance of letting pupils make errors. Enhancing one's capacity for problem-solving, building resilience, and boosting one's self-assurance may be accomplished by fostering an atmosphere where mistakes are viewed as chances for development and learning. In the following paragraphs, we'll look at the importance of allowing students make errors and how it affects their whole educational experience.

THEORETICAL BASIS

Tips and techniques to implement

Correction should be timely and focused. When students make mistakes, teachers should provide timely correction and clarification, focusing just on the specific mistake made. Overcorrection can demotivate students.

Establish a safe and encouraging learning environment: It's critical to establish an environment in the classroom where pupils feel at ease making errors. Encourage pupils to take chances, make mistakes, and stress that learning is a process that includes making mistakes.

Be selective and consistent. Choose a few types of errors to focus on with each student or group. Consistently correcting the same errors will help students improve. Sort out the most significant errors: Focus on fixing the errors that are impeding the student's understanding and communication abilities initially. Don't go over each and every error. Determine frequent mistakes: Start by listing the usual mistakes that learners of English make whether speaking or writing it. This can be accomplished by monitoring how they speak and by reviewing what they produce.

1. When pointing out an erroneous phoneme, use the phonemic chart: This method is effective for fixing pronunciation issues in TEFL lessons. It involves the teacher pointing out a particular sound that a pupil has mispronounced using a phonemic chart, which displays all the sounds of a language. The teacher can assist pupils in recognizing their errors and making the required corrections to enhance their pronunciation by graphically displaying the ideal sound. This method works especially well for difficult-to-distinguish sounds, such as the differences between the English "th" and "s" sounds. For instance, the difference between the sounds that the letters "th" in "the" and "think" or the letters "s" in "sit" and those in "sugar" convey¹.

2. Mistakes in Writing

Outside of necessary testing, red pen corrections for writing mistakes should be avoided: When reviewing papers, simply striking off the incorrect response and writing the right one is quicker, but when working one-on-one with kids, it is like to mowing the lawn while maintaining a garden. Instead of leaving a trace of lessons learnt, red markings serve as a stark reminder of a mistake. Instead, teachers should assist students with their writing and editing while, if feasible, allowing them to edit their own work. The student's self-confidence will be maintained, and doing so will support the development of individual learning methodologies. The form of feedback is crucial for both groups: "Oh, that's close," you say. A considerably more motivating statement than "That's wrong" is "You've almost got it!" In terms of classroom management generally, telling students to "don't run" is less successful than telling them to "walk slowly." Students will use

¹ <https://teflbarcelona.net/mastering-error-correction-6-effective-techniques-for-tefl-teachers-part-2/>

communication techniques including repeating, responding, and questioning in conversation as clues to assess their own clarity and try self-correction. Although prompts have some effectiveness, it's crucial to avoid taking over the discourse. When students express their own ideas and words, language acquisition becomes more natural. If at all, direct adjustments need to be utilized as a last option.²

3. This method is a straightforward yet efficient strategy to help students in a TEFL class improve their sentence structure and word order. Cross over arm correction for incorrect word order. When a pupil makes a mistake in word order, the teacher crosses their arms to indicate that the phrase needs to be reconstructed. Once the proper word order has been accomplished, the learner is asked to restate the statement. Students who have trouble with English word order and syntax will benefit the most from using this method. The "cross over arm" approach aids pupils in identifying and fixing their mistakes in real-time by seeing and interactively revising sentence structure.³

4. Tell them how many mistakes

This technique is best suited for controlled speaking practice, but it may be a very straightforward approach to provide feedback in that circumstance. The phrases "most of the comparatives were right, but you made two mistakes" and "three words are in the wrong position in the sentence/are mixed up" are examples. Use this strategy only when pupils can recall the material you're referring to without excessive prompting.

Other appropriate words:

(For a tongue twister) "excellent attempt/ Getting better, but at two instances you uttered /sh/ where it should have been /s/. Very excellent, however you made only one error with the passive. Do you know which words they are?"⁴

5. Just tell them they are wrong (but nicely)

"Nearly there," "getting closer," "just one mistake," "much better," "good idea, but...," "I understand what you mean, but...," "you have made a mistake that almost everyone does/that's a very common mistake," "we haven't studied this yet," "much better pronunciation, but..." and "much better pronunciation, but..." are all examples of positive ways to be negative. With lower level and new courses, you might have to strike a balance between the want to be kind and the desire to be clear and avoid perplexing them with feedback language that they don't understand, possibly by limiting your feedback language for the first few months to one or two words. Giving students translations of this and other classroom terminology you plan to use, for instance on a worksheet or a poster, might also be helpful.⁵

6. Short story with common errors: Using this method, teachers may detect and correct frequent mistakes made by their pupils while simultaneously providing linguistic input. It requires the teacher creating a little story that contains typical grammatical mistakes committed by the students. For their homework assignment, the students are then tasked with locating and fixing the story's mistakes. This method enables students to interact meaningfully and contextually with the language while also assisting them in identifying and correcting their mistakes. Additionally, by

² <https://www.teflcourse.net/blog/corrections-techniques-ittt-tefl-blog/>

³ <https://teflbarcelona.net/mastering-error-correction-6-effective-techniques-for-tefl-teachers-part-2/>

⁴ <https://www.tefl.net/elt/ideas/speak/correcting-spoken-errors/>

⁵ <https://www.tefl.net/elt/ideas/speak/correcting-spoken-errors/>

assigning the narrative as homework, teachers provide students the chance to practice their language abilities on their own, at their own speed, and in a pleasant and interesting way.⁶

RESULT

Making mistakes and errors can really be a very beneficial component of learning, particularly when learning a new language. Here are some potential results:

- ✓ Mistakes help us remember and understand things better. According to research, making mistakes and fixing them improves conceptual understanding and recall. Errors bring pupils' attention to important information and connections that they might have otherwise missed.
- ✓ Mistakes enhance metacognition. It helps students develop metacognitive abilities including self-monitoring, self-assessment, and cognitive flexibility as they recognize, examine, and fix their own mistakes. These competencies are crucial for lifelong learning. Students learn how to correct themselves. Allowing pupils to make mistakes helps them learn how to self-correct and self-regulate their language usage. They learn more independently as a result of this.
- ✓ Mistakes encourage active learning. When students make mistakes, they find themselves compelled to reflect critically on why the mistake occurred and how to fix it. The students' active problem-solving and self-analysis can help solidify the appropriate knowledge and abilities in their thoughts. Correcting mistakes helps students learn what is correct and improve for the future⁷
- ✓ Mistakes provide feedback. When pupils make mistakes, the teacher can see which ideas or abilities they are having trouble with. The teacher can use this feedback to modify their teaching styles and explanations to better suit the requirements of the pupils. Also, Mistakes can highlight knowledge weaknesses in students. Teachers can spot knowledge gaps or misunderstandings in their pupils by looking at the types of mistakes they consistently make. This offers chances for specialized teaching to close those gaps.
- ✓ Making mistakes boosts confidence. Students' anxiety is reduced and their self-confidence is boosted when they realize that making errors is a normal part of learning and that doing so is not punished. This is crucial for learning a language.⁸

DISCUSSION

It is not uncommon for English language lessons to favour communication over accuracy: real life is nothing like a classroom! In real-life situations, when you make a mistake in the language you are learning, context provides ample information as to what the intended message is. In fact, most of the time, impeccable accuracy is not needed at all! 'Don't worry about making mistakes,' I used to tell my English language students, 'communicating is the most important thing!'⁹

Learning a Language Means Making Mistakes

Making mistakes when speaking or writing a new language is not the same as making certain other kinds of mistakes, at least to me. Making mistakes when learning a language is not only necessary, it is a good sign. If you are not making mistakes you are not trying hard enough to use the language.

⁶ <https://teflbarcelona.net/mastering-error-correction-6-effective-techniques-for-tefl-teachers-part-2/>

⁷ <https://www.kirstenskaboodle.com/the-benefits-of-making-mistakes/>

⁸ <https://www.romper.com/p/let-your-child-make-mistakes-for-these-7-benefits-experts-say-19454963>

⁹ Maija Kozlova, <https://www.cambridgeenglish.org/blog/authors/maiya-kozlova/>

Give Your Brain Time

If you are trying to master English, or any other new language, there are certain things that you are not going to remember, or get right, until your brain is ready. All you can do is to continue to use the language as much as possible, to read, to listen and to speak and write. Eventually that elusive word, or that difficult phrase, will start to become natural.¹⁰

Language acquisition expert Wilga Rivers believes teachers should "tolerate error-filled speech" in the early stages of language learning. Students need a safe space to experiment and take risks.

According to many experts, allowing pupils to make errors and giving the proper amount of correction and feedback seems to be ideal for language learning growth. The idea is to foster an environment in the classroom where students are free to take chances and learn from their mistakes.

SUMMARY

In conclusion, a growth mindset that sees mistakes as a normal and valuable aspect of learning might encourage students to feel more at ease taking risks, thinking outside the box, and eventually improving their language abilities. The goal is for educators to normalize mistakes, offer direction and criticism, and aid students in making sense of their blunders. Students benefit most from learning from their own errors when teachers offer prompt criticism and direction. Instead of only pointing out problems, the teacher's job is to assist pupils in understanding and fixing their errors. It is also worth mentioning that mistakes should not be tolerated at all since doing so can inhibit learning, yet accepting mistakes as a necessary element of learning can hasten student development. Students will be better prepared to make errors and learn from them in the real world if they are allowed to do so now in a low-stakes setting.

The author also recommends that educators provide pupils constructive criticism so they may learn from their mistakes. This entails giving both encouraging comments to help perpetuate proper language usage and focused feedback to fix mistakes.

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